

IMPROVED YOUNG'S MODULUS OF GRAPHENE PAPERS MADE FROM LARGE GRAPHENE OXIDE SHEETS

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1 Introduction

Graphene, a two-dimensional, one-atomic thick carbon material, is the versatile building block for many carbon-based strong and stiff materials given its exceptional mechanical properties [1]. Graphene oxide (GO) is the oxygenated derivative of graphene covered with hydroxyl and epoxy groups on the basal plane as well as carboxyl groups at the edges [2]. These functional groups provide GO with excellent solubility in water, allowing one to produce a large quantity of graphene sheets from the natural graphite. GO nanosheets have been used to fabricate various new class of materials, such as GO papers, GO/carbon nanotube hybrid films and GO/polymer nanocomposites.

GO papers can be easily fabricated by stacking GO sheets via flow-directed filtration of aqueous GO dispersion. This new material outperforms other paper-like materials in terms of mechanical properties, with its Young's modulus significantly higher than that of carbon nanotube bucky papers or inorganic vermiculite films [3]. The combination of such exceptional mechanical properties with other intriguing functional properties, such as thermal stability [4], high electrical conductivity [5] and biocompatibility [6], makes GO papers a very promising candidate for many technological applications: e.g., free-standing flexible electrodes for Li-ion batteries and supercapacitors [7-8], biomedical applications such as inclusion in heart

valves and drug delivery [9], transparent conducting films [10-11] and nanocomposites [12-13].

Among the many parameters that affect the Young's modulus of GO papers, the lateral dimension of precursor GO sheets plays an important role. Large area GO sheets are ideally suited in a number of applications: e.g. 3D graphene-based networks in self-assembled hydrogels [14], formation of liquid crystals in an aqueous solution [15], 2D aligned structure in polymer-based composites [12] and conductive thin films for optoelectronic devices [10-11]. However, it is necessary to understand as to how and to what extent the size of GO sheets can affect the properties of GO papers, including the Young's modulus, as well as the underlying mechanisms.

In this paper, molecular dynamics simulations (MDSs) are used to predict the Young's modulus of GO papers consisting of different GO sizes. The alignment of the GO sheets in GO papers is quantitatively assessed using the fast Fourier transform (FFT) method. The interactions between GO sheets of different sizes are evaluated at atomic level to identify the dominant mechanisms underlying the GO size-property relationship.

2 Molecular dynamic simulations

2.1 Models

Two sets of GO paper models with and without incorporated water molecules (Fig. 1) were built using monolayer GO sheets. For each set of models with and without water (Fig. 1), five different

models with the same number of carbon atoms and different GO lengths were constructed with periodic boundary conditions imposed along the short (y-axis) and out-of-plane (z-axis) directions. A 100-Å-thick vacuum slab was imposed along the loading direction (x-axis) to prevent any interaction between the periodic images. GO sheets were stacked in a hierarchical manner with individual lengths approximately 1.1 nm (Fig. 2a), 2.0 nm, 2.4 nm, 3.5 nm and 5.4 nm (Fig. 2b) along the x-axis and a constant width of 2.46nm (Fig. 2c) in the y-axis. Epoxy and hydroxyl groups were randomly distributed along both sides of graphene basal plane while carboxyl groups were attached to the edge. These models yielded C/O ratios ranging from 2.17 for the smallest size to 2.68 for the largest size, in agreement with the experimental study [16]. For models without water molecules, an interlayer distance of 6 Å was chosen according to the previous findings [17]. For those with water, water molecules were randomly added to the structures, yielding a moisture content of 16 w.t.% and an interlayer distance of 9 Å according to the experimental analysis [16].

2.2 Simulation methods

MDSs were carried out using the program, Materials Studio (Accelrys). The Condensed-Phase Optimized Molecular Potentials for Atomistic Simulation Studies (COMPASS) force field [18] was used to simulate interatomic interactions. All the simulations were carried out in the canonical ensemble where the total number of atoms N and the volume V remained constant with a time step of 1 fs. The temperature was maintained at 1 K using Andersen thermostat. The Verlet algorithm [19] was used for the integration of the Newton's equation of motion. The group-based cutoff distance for non-bond interactions was 9.5 Å. Energy minimization was performed using a conjugate-gradient algorithm implemented in Materials Studio to maintain the total potential energy of the system minimum.

2.3 Calculation of Young's modulus

The Young's moduli of GO paper models were obtained from the energy-strain curves. The boundary carbon atoms at the right edge were fixed and a displacement ΔL was applied to the carbon atoms at the left edge. The system was then relaxed for 10 ps with a subsequent minimization process to

reach equilibrium. The temperature was maintained at 1K to avoid thermal effects. The Young's modulus, E , is defined as:

$$E = \frac{\sigma}{\varepsilon} = \frac{F/A}{\Delta L/L_x} = \frac{FL_x}{A\Delta L} \quad (1)$$

where $A = L_y h$ is the cross-sectional area; h is the thickness of the model; And L_x is the total length of the model along the x-axis. F is the force acting on the carbon atoms along the x-axis, which is expressed as:

$$F = \frac{EA\Delta L}{L_x} \quad (2)$$

The strain energy, U , was calculated as:

$$U = \int F dL = \frac{1}{2} EV \varepsilon^2 \quad (3)$$

where $V = AL_x$ is the volume of the model. The Young's modulus is then given by:

$$E = \frac{1}{V} \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial \varepsilon^2} \quad (4)$$

2.4 Calculation of interaction energy

The interaction potential energy between two adjacent GO sheets was calculated as:

$$U_{int} = |U_{A,B} - (U_A + U_B)| \quad (5)$$

where U_A and U_B are the potential energies of two isolated GO sheets, and $U_{A,B}$ is the total potential energy of the assembly.

2.5 Extrapolation of Young's modulus

Due to the limitation of computational capability, the size of simulation models was set on the nano-scale, which was much smaller than the micro-scale of the samples used in experiments. Therefore, the simulation results were extrapolated to predict the Young's modulus of papers with GO sheets on the micro-scale by logarithmic fitting:

$$E = a - b \ln(L + c) \quad (6)$$

where E is the Young's modulus (GPa); L is the length of individual GO sheet (in nm); and a , b and c are the coefficients to be fitted by the experimental data.

2.6 Deformation of GO papers

All calculations of deformation were conducted based on the same strain level of 0.4%. Supposing ΔL_{total} denotes the total deformation of GO papers, ΔL_{total} is given by the sum of two components: (i) elongation of each GO sheet, $\Delta L_{GO\ sheet}$ and (ii) elongation of the gap between them in the same horizontal plane, $\Delta L_{inter-sheet}$:

$$\Delta L_{total} = \Sigma \Delta L_{GO\ sheets} + \Sigma \Delta L_{inter-sheet} \quad (7)$$

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Effect of GO size on Young's modulus of GO papers

The energy-strain curves for the GO papers with different precursor GO sheet sizes are shown in Figs 3a and 3b. The potential energy increased parabolically with strain for all GO sizes, indicating a linear response of the stress with applied strain. The Young's moduli of the GO papers both with and without water molecules increased consistently as the GO sheet size increased by about five times from 1.1 nm to 5.4 nm, as shown in Fig. 4a. For the models containing the same size GO sheets, GO papers with water always showed higher Young's moduli than their counterparts without water due to the increased number of inter-layer hydrogen bonds mediated by water molecules [17]. The results were extrapolated using a logarithmic equation, as shown in Fig. 4b, to estimate the dependence of Young's modulus on GO size on the micrometer scale, as seen in practical GO papers. The comparison between the extrapolated curve and the experimental data [14] indicates that while the MD simulation correctly predicted the general trend, the predictions were approximately an order of magnitude higher than the experimental results. Such a large discrepancy is expected and can be attributed to the idealized, defect-free models used in the simulation, whereas the GO paper samples tested in experiments always contained crumpled and folded GO sheets with defects induced during the oxidation process. Misalignments between the GO sheets in the experimental GO papers have also contributed significantly to the discrepancy. Both the load transfer efficiency between adjacent GO sheets and the inherent stiffness of individual GO were greatly reduced due to these structural flaws.

There are a few reasons that may be responsible for the improved Young's modulus of GO papers with large GO sheets. The simulation results indicate that upon equilibrium the GO papers with larger GO sheets had a more compact and aligned structure than that with smaller GO sheets, as shown in Fig. 5. It appears that the larger GO sheets led to a more efficient load transfer between them. To substantiate this finding, we used the FFT method to quantitatively evaluate the degree of alignment of GO papers based on the SEM images, which is discussed in the next section. Another reason may be related to the different deformation mechanisms of GO papers with different GO sizes. This is also discussed at length in Section 3.3.

3.2 Alignment of GO sheet in GO papers

The FFT method was shown to be a powerful tool to measure the orientation properties of fibers in fiber reinforced composites [20]. The FFT was performed on an area $2\ \mu\text{m} \times 4\ \mu\text{m}$ of scanning electron microscope (SEM) images, which were taken from the GO paper samples made from small GO sheets (average area $\sim 1.07\ \mu\text{m}^2$) and large GO sheets (average area $\sim 272.2\ \mu\text{m}^2$). The FFT converted the complex spatial patterns represented by gray values in each pixel $I[m, n]$ of the SEM images into direction-dependent frequency domain images $F[u, v]$ by:

$$F[u, v] = \frac{1}{MN} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} I[m, n] \cdot e^{-i2\pi \left(\frac{um}{M} + \frac{vn}{N} \right)} \quad (8)$$

The intensity of each pixel in the frequency domain images showed an angular dependence on the patterns of spatial alignment where pixels with high intensity values clustered along the orientation of the highest degree of directional anisotropy. The angular distribution of the intensity in the frequency domain images followed the Cauchy-Lorentz distribution:

$$y = y_0 + \frac{2A}{\pi} \cdot \left(\frac{w}{4(x-x_0)^2 + w^2} \right) \quad (9)$$

The degree of alignment was quantitatively measured by the scale parameter, w , which represents the angle deviation from the principle orientation. A smaller w value means better spatial alignment.

The SEM images together with their FFT frequency images and angular distributions are shown in Fig. 6.

The w values for GO papers with small GO and large GO sizes were 36.2 and 20, respectively, clearly demonstrating better alignment of the larger GO sheets in GO papers.

3.3 Deformation mechanisms of GO papers with different GO sheet sizes

To understand the mechanisms behind the improved Young's modulus, a further probe was made into the exact deformation mechanisms between the GO sheets. There are two components of deformation which contribute to the total tensile deformation of GO papers: namely, (i) GO sheets deformation, i.e., elongation of GO sheets themselves as a result of stretching, bending and torsion of carbon-carbon bonds within the GO sheets; and (ii) inter-sheet deformation taking place in the form of relative displacement between the GO sheets in the same as well as in the different horizontal plane(s) causing stretching of hydrogen bonds formed between the functional groups both in tension and shear. The contributions of the two different components to the total deformation of GO papers are plotted as a function of GO size in Fig. 7. It is found that more than 90% of the deformation originated from the inter-sheet deformation regardless of the GO size on the nano-scale. The extrapolation also indicates that the contribution from the deformation of GO sheets increased linearly as the GO size increases, reaching almost 20% of the total when the average GO size is above 50 nm. This observation implies that the tensile deformation of GO papers is dominated by the inter-sheet deformation while the elongation of the GO sheets becomes increasingly more important as the GO size increases.

Because the inter-sheet deformation is the major component of deformation in GO papers, the next question is why the papers made from larger size GO can resist inter-sheet deformation more efficiently to yield a higher Young's modulus. The inter-sheet deformation was hindered by the interactions between adjacent sheets both in the same and different horizontal planes through hydrogen bonds. As shown in Fig. 8, the edge-to-edge interaction is defined as the interaction occurring between adjacent GO sheets in the same horizontal plane while the face-to-face interaction as that occurring in different horizontal planes. The energies arising from these interactions are plotted as a function of GO sheet length in Fig. 9. Although

the former energy component remained almost the same low value, the latter component increased due to the increasing contact area. The face-to-face interaction energy component dominated in impeding the inter-sheet deformation of GO papers as it became increasingly higher than the energy component due to edge-to-edge interactions when the GO size increased. This observation is directly translated into increasing interactions between adjacent GO sheets, discouraging the inter-sheet deformation and consequently enhanced Young's modulus. Apart from the above inter-sheet interactions, the elongation of GO sheets themselves also became more important with increasing GO size, although it still remained as a minor contribution. GO sheet deformation caused stretching of carbon-carbon covalent bonds within the GO sheets, requiring more energy than simply stretching the weak inter-sheet hydrogen bonds like in inter-sheet deformation. Because the contribution of GO sheet deformation continuously increased with GO size, more energy was required to deform GO papers and consequently a higher Young's modulus was expected.

4 Conclusion

This paper studies the effect of lateral size of GO sheets on the Young's modulus of GO papers based on MDSs. The Young's modulus of GO papers both with and without water molecules increased with increasing GO size. The Young's modulus of GO papers with water always showed higher values than their counterparts of the same size without water. The GO papers made from larger GO sheets showed better alignment than those with smaller sheets, as confirmed by the FFT analysis. The dominant mechanisms underlying the improvement of Young's modulus by increasing the GO size were revealed by investigating the deformation mechanism of GO papers. The shear interactions between adjacent graphene sheets in different planes played a key role in resisting the deformation of GO papers on the nanoscale. The stretching of GO sheets themselves in tension also became increasingly important when GO size was increased.

The above findings have useful implications in GO/polymer nanocomposites where large size GO sheets can enhance the interface shear stress transfer between the GO sheets and polymer matrix.

Fig. 1. 3D model snapshots of GO papers with and without water molecules.

Fig. 2. Initial configurations of MDS models of GO paper: x-z plane view of the model with GO length of (a) 1.1 nm; and (b) 5.4 nm. (c) x-y plane view where the widths of all models are identical.

Fig. 3. Energy-strain curves of GO papers with different GO size (a) with and (b) without water.

Fig. 4. (a) Plots of Young's modulus as a function of GO length; and (b) extrapolation of modulus values.

Fig. 5. GO paper models with GO length (a) 1.1 nm and (b) 5.4 nm after equilibrium. The larger GO sheets showed better alignment than smaller ones.

Fig. 6. SEM images (left), FFT frequency domain images (middle) and angular distributions fitted by Cauchy-Lorentz distributions (right) for GO papers with (a) small GO sheets (average area $\sim 1.07 \mu\text{m}^2$) and (b) large GO sheets (average area $\sim 272.2 \mu\text{m}^2$).

Fig. 7. Plots of two different components of deformation as a function of GO length. Solid and dash lines are linear extrapolation of the experimental data.

Fig. 8. 2D illustration of face-to-face and edge-to-edge interactions.

Fig. 9. Plots of face-to-face and edge-to-edge interaction energies as a function of GO length.

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